

SEARCH TECHNIQUES

Boolean Search

This is a very common search technique that combines search terms according to the Boolean logic. Three types of Boolean search are possible: AND search, OR search and NOT search.

Boolean AND

Search allows users to combine two or more search terms using the Boolean AND operator. A Boolean AND search will retrieve all those items where all the constituent terms occur. For example, the following search expression "Internet and WWW" will retrieve all those records where both the terms occur. Boolean AND search adds more restrictions to a search expression by adding more search terms. Therefore, the more search terms are ANDed, the more restricted, or specific, will be the search, and as a result the less will be the search output. Sometime, a search may not produce any result if too many search terms are ANDed.

Boolean OR

Search allows users to combine two or more search terms such that the system retrieves all those items that contain either one or all of the constituent terms. Thus, the following search expression "Colleges or Universities" will retrieve all those records (1) where the term Colleges occurs, (2) where the term Universities occurs, and (3) where both the terms occur. Note that this is opposite to the usage of the term 'or' in regular English. Boolean OR search; though adds more terms to a search expression, adds less restrictions to a given search expression, because the search is conducted for occurrence of each single ORed term irrespective of whether the other term(s) occurs or not. Consequently, the output of OR searches will be more. When there are too many search terms bRed, the search output may be too big to handle.

Boolean NOT

A search lets users specify those terms they don't want to appear in the retrieved records. For example, the search phrase "Search engines NOT Hotbot" will return all the records on search engines except those where the word 'Hotbot' appears. Boolean NOT searches introduce limits to a search because the search system is made to exclude those items that were to contain the NOT term(s). Therefore, the search output will decrease with increase in the NOT terms. The operators used for conducting a Boolean search vary form one search system to the other

TruncationSearch

Truncation is the searching facility where a search can be carried out on all the different forms of a word that have got the same common root. To illustrate, the truncated word COMPUTER will bring out items on the terms COMPUTER, COMPUTING, COMPUTATION,

COMPUTE, etc. Many different choices are available when truncating, namely: right truncation, left truncation, and middle letter masking. Left truncation retrieves all words having the same characters at the right hand part, for example, '*hyl' will retrieve words like 'methyl', 'ethyl', etc. Similarly, middle truncation retrieves all words having the same characters at the left and right hand part. For example, a middle truncated search term 'col*r' will retrieve both the terms 'colour' and 'color'. A 'wild card' is used to allow any letter to appear in a specific location within a word. Right truncation and character masking or wild card are the most common truncation search facilities available in search systems. Operators used for, truncation search vary from one information retrieval system to another; the most commonly used truncation operators include: *, \$,!, and?

Proximity Search

This search facility enables a user to specify (1) whether two search terms should occur adjacent to each other, (2) whether one or more words occur in between the search terms, (3) whether the search terms should occur in the same paragraph irrespective of the intervening words, and so on. The operators used for proximity search and their meaning vary from one search system to the other. A proximity search is as good as a Boolean And search, in that it searches for two or more search terms occurrences in the documents. However, it imposes further constraints in indicating the distance between the occurrences of the search terms, so the search output becomes more specified..

Field-Specific Search

A search can be conducted on all the fields in a database, or it may be restricted to one or more chosen fields to produce more specific results. Specific fields and codes vary according to the search systems and database. The following examples show some valid pIALOG searches that have been restricted to some specific fields. The general 'format for using suffix codes is "Syntax: SELECT / xx.xx :. where xx is a Basic Index field code(s)"

Limiting Search

Sometimes a user might want to limit a particular search using specific criteria like language, year of publication, type of information sources and so on. These are called limiting searches. The parameters which can be used to limit a search are determined by the database concerned. The following are some examples of limiting searches in DIALOG:

8 Range Search

Range search is extremely useful with numerical information. It is crucial in choosing records within specific data ranges. The following options are usually available for range searching,

though the exact number of operators, their meaning etc., differ from one search system to another: